

How to Find and Access data in Europe

A practical introduction

Irena Vipavc Brvar, ADP and Jennifer Buckley, UKDS

Overview

1. Data types and sources
2. Identify what you need
3. Searching data archives
4. Evaluating data: quality and usefulness
5. Accessing data

Practical activities

⇒ find and evaluate the usefulness of data for a specific research question

1 Data types and sources

Activity 1

Your knowledge and experience of the data landscape

List

- types and sources of data you know
- how you have/might use archived data

<https://wall2.sli.do/event/g8xaftqc>

Types of data

Thinking about the types of data available can help you work out what you need and how to find it.

Quantitative and Qualitative

CESSDA Training Working Group (2017)

Types of data: level of analysis

Macro data

- Aggregate
 - about populations, groups, regions and countries constructed by combining information on lower level units (e.g. unemployment rate, fertility)
- System level
 - characteristics of higher-level units such as the state or the political system e.g. electoral system (PR or single-member districts) and member of EU

Meso data

- data on collective and cooperative actors such as commercial companies, organizations or political parties

Microdata

- data from individual units (often people or households) often from surveys, a census and administrative records

Types of data: time

Cross-sectional	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• one-point of time (a snap shot)• usually information on multiple cases and variables
Repeated cross sectional	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• cross-sectional surveys repeated with new samples• data from the different samples allows analysis of trends
Time series	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• series of data points in time order (often equally spaced in time)• aggregate macro data are often time-series data.• time points may come from sample surveys e.g. unemployment from labour force surveys
Longitudinal	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• follow the same units over time e.g. household panel studies collect information from a sample of households in regular 'waves'

Sources of data

There are many sources of data

CESSDA Training Working Group (2017)

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Sources of data: European social science data archives

SND Swedish National Data Service

Data collections include:

- variation between archives
- quantitative data - major source of individual level data
- qualitative
- outputs of
 - major academic projects
 - government/policy
 - small research teams
 - individual researchers
- recent and less recent data
- different languages

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Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives

*"enabling the research
community to conduct high-
quality research in the social
science"*

Key tasks

- Developing standards and best practices
 - Facilitating access to important data resources
- Work done by developing tools, training and co-ordinating network

Members

- » Austria
- » Belgium
- » Czech Republic
- » Denmark
- » France
- » Finland
- » Germany
- » Greece
- » Hungary
- » Netherlands
- » Norway
- » Portugal
- » Slovakia
- » Slovenia
- » Sweden
- » *Switzerland*
- » UK

National data services

Activities include

- checking the quality of data and metadata
- maintaining catalogues
- managing access to data through appropriate licensing
- obtaining data
- training for both those creating and using data

Open Access to research data (European Commission)

Open access (OA) can be defined as the practice of providing on-line access to scientific information that is free of charge to the user and that is re-usable. Open access to 'scientific information' refers to two main categories:

Peer-reviewed scientific publications (primarily research articles published in academic journals)

Scientific research data: data underlying publications and/or other data (such as curated but unpublished datasets or raw data)

AS OPEN AS POSSIBLE, AS CLOSED AS NECESSARY

Source

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HOW IT WORKS

 #openaccess
#opendata
#H2020

Source: EC

Open Access to research data

-> importance of research infrastructures / data repositories

Source: EC

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Horizon Europe

2021-2027

Reinforce openness

Open Science will become the modus operandi of Horizon Europe. It will go beyond the open access policy of Horizon 2020 and require open access to publications, data, and to research data management plans.

Source: EC

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Slovenian Social Science Data Archives (ADP)

- Founded in 1997
- Slovenian national data repository for social sciences
- 600 social science surveys with data in a data catalogue + 150 with metadata
- Cca. 800 users registered in 2017 (90 % education, 10 % scientific/research purpose)
- 168 survey data used for detailed secondary-analysis in 2017

ADP - SOCIAL SCIENCE DATA ARCHIVES

Analyze data! Deposit study! Promote science!

1997 →

USE DATA DEPOSIT STUDY LEARN ABOUT DISCOVER ADP

SEARCH

HOW TO GET DATA?

FIND → REGISTER → ANALYZE →

HOW TO DEPOSIT DATA?

RECORD → PREPARE → DEPOSIT →

BLOG NEWS EXPOSED

11. July 2018 Poročilo z delavnice 'Legal and ethical issues of combining survey data with new forms of data'

11. July 2018 Direktiva o avtorskih pravicah in interes raziskovalne skupnosti

11. July 2018 Konferenca Spolna diferenciacija v medijski industriji

6. July 2018 Vodič za pripravo transkriptov v družboslovju

5. July 2018 Raziskovalke s Fakultete za družbene vede predstavile prispevek na konferenci WAPOR 2018

WHAT WE DO

20TH ANNIVERSARY

WITH YOU FOR 20 YEARS

RECENTLY ADDED STUDIES

ADP ACTIVITIES

CONFERENCES AND EVENTS

- ❑ Oldest data sets in the archive (public opinion polls) are from 1966
- ❑ Wide range of topics covered
- ❑ In most cases data relates only to Slovenia / few international
- ❑ Metadata in SI en EN, Datafiles mostly in SI

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UK Data Service

Access to the UK's largest collection of social, economic and population data
Support for users with training and guidance.

- ❑ major UK and cross-national surveys
- ❑ longitudinal studies (household panel and cohort studies)
- ❑ UK Census 1971-2011
- ❑ qualitative data collections
- ❑ research data in a researcher repository (Reshare)

Browse by Topic

Users have two options for identifying studies related to a particular topic.

- *Topic Classifications* address topics broadly, and are meant to be a good starting point for exploring the collection.
- The [Thesaurus](#) contains both broad and narrow terms that are more specific to the subject matter of individual studies.
- Our [Thematic Collections](#) are full websites that focus on particular subject areas.

Topic Classifications

[Census Enumerations](#)

[Historical and Contemporary Population Characteristics](#)

[View More](#)

[Community and Urban Studies](#)

[View More](#)

[Conflict, Aggression, Violence, Wars](#)

[View More](#)

[Economic Behavior and Attitudes](#)

[View More](#)

[Education](#)

[Elites and Leadership](#)

[Geography and Environment](#)

[Government Structures, Policies, and Capabilities](#)

ICPSR

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Cross-national studies

International survey research programmes include many European countries

-
- International Social Survey Programme (ISSP)
 - European Social Survey
 - European Values Survey
 - Eurobarometer
 - Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement Europe (SHARE)
 - Generations and gender programme (GGP)

Cross-national studies

International Social Survey Programme (ISSP)

- annual programme (started in 1984)
- cross-national collaboration
- rotating thematic modules e.g.
 - Citizenship: 2004 and 2014
 - Work Orientations: 1989, 1997, 2005, 2015
 - Role of Government: 1985, 1990, 1996, 2006, 2016

Data Download

[Data Catalogue](#)

gesis
Leibniz-Institut
für Sozialwissenschaften

CESSDA ERIC

- [-] ZACAT
 - [-] ISSP
 - [+] by Year
 - [+] by Module Topic
 - [+] Cumulations
 - [+] CSES
 - [-] Eurobarometer
 - [+] Standard & Special Eurobarometer
 - [+] Central and Eastern Eurobarometer
 - [+] Candidate Countries Eurobarometer
 - [+] European Values Study (EVS)
 - [+] Studies from Eastern Europe
 - [+] ALLBUS (GGSS)
 - [+] Politbarometer (German documentation only)
 - [+] Election Studies (Germany)
 - [+] Childhood, adolescence and becoming an adult 1991-1997 (bilingual documentation)
 - [+] LebensRäume

ZACAT - GESIS Online Study Catalogue

Welcome to ZACAT, a social science data portal allowing you to search for, browse, analyse and download social science survey data, provided by **GESIS - Leibniz Institute for the Social Sciences** (dept. Data Archive for the Social Sciences).

The studies in this catalogue are a small selection of the **data available at GESIS**. Further studies are added continuously to ZACAT (see box at the right for recent publications).

Use of ZACAT is free of charge. Published datasets and accompanying documentation can be browsed without prior registration. Analysing, creating tables and downloading require accepting the **GESIS terms of use**.

Please click on **+** in the left frame to view the ZACAT catalogue structure. If you click on the name (and not

Recent Datasets / Collections	
2018-08-21	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Eurobarometer 88.4 (December 2017): Sport and physical activity, and EU citizens, Agriculture and the CAP (ZA6939), version 1.0.0 (2018-08-10), doi:10.4232/1.13065 ▶ Eurobarometer 83.1 (February-March 2015): Europeans in 2015, Data Protection and the Internet (ZA5964), version 2.0.0 (2018-08-10), doi: ZA5964 1.13071
2018-07-06	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Allgemeine Bevölkerungsumfrage der Sozialwissenschaften ALLBUS - Kumulation 1980-2016 (ZA4586), version 1.0.0 (2018-06-07), doi:10.4232/1.13029
2018-06-21	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Eurobarometer 82.4 (November-December 2014): The European Parliament (Parlemeter 2014), Autonomous Systems, Gender Equality, and Smoking Habits (ZA5933), version 6.0.0 (2018-06-20), doi:10.4232/1.13044
2018-06-05	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Eurobarometer 82.3 (November 2014): Europe

Cross-national studies

Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement Europe (SHARE)

- longitudinal study
- more than 123,000 individuals aged 50
- 27 European countries and Israel
- health, socio-economic status and social and family networks

Select Country

Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe

Home

Organisation

Data Access

Data Documentation

Special Data Sets

SHARE Publications

Press & News

Contact

You are here: Home

SHARE - Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe

The Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe (SHARE) is a multidisciplinary and cross-national panel database of micro data on health, socio-economic status and social and family networks of approximately 123,000 individuals aged 50 or older (more than 293,000 interviews). SHARE covers **27 European countries and Israel**.

The **data** are available to the entire research community **free of charge**. For a summary overview and research results of SHARE, you can download the **SHARE brochure** or our latest First Results Book: **Ageing in Europe - Supporting Policies for an Inclusive Society**.

Search search

News

Wave 6 data released!
SHARE is very happy to announce the release of Wave 6 data! Wave 6 not only includes Croatia as a...

[read more...](#)

Launch of the Executive Master's Programme in Management of Research Infrastructures

Rltrain, the Research Infrastructure Training Programme, is launching its Executive Master's...

[read more...](#)

SHARE Newsletter No. 20
Please enjoy reading our Newsletter No. 20. In this edition, we present to you three of our new...

[read more...](#)

Newsletter

Latest Newsletter

Subscribe to the SHARE newsletter by sending an e-mail to info@share-project.org

Cross-national studies

European Social Survey (ESS)

- A biennial cross-national survey (started in 2002)
- Highest methodological standard

	R1 2002	R2 2004	R3 2006	R4 2008	R5 2010	R6 2012	R7 2014	R8 2016
Media and social trust	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•
Politics	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•
Subjective well-being...	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•
Gender, Household	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•
Socio demographics	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•
Human values	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•
Immigration	•						•	
Citizen involvement	•							
Health and care		•						
Economic morality		•						
Family work and well-being		•			•			

freely available data for 36 countries.

23 countries in 2016

Probably most used / cited data. 125 T registered users, 89 T data downloads.

Source: [ESS](#)

CESSDA ERIC

Topline Results issue 6 out now

Our report identifies rates of self-diagnosed physical and mental health conditions in 21 European nations.

[More...](#)

Does the applicant suffer from any disease likely to interfere with the sufficient driver, or to cause driving by him source of danger to the public? YES, please specify

Social Inequalities in Health and their Determinants

Topline Results from Round 7 of the European Social Survey

Latest news

06/04/17

General Assembly meeting later this month

27/03/17

Madrid to host latest event

24/03/17

ESS presents at European conferences

13/03/17

Roger Jowell Memorial Lecture 2017

Data and Documentation

Data and documentation can be accessed by round (year), by theme or by country. Data are available for download and online analysis.

Methodological Research

The European Social Survey runs a programme of research to support and enhance the methodology that underpins the high standards it pursues in every aspect of survey design, data collection and archiving.

Examples: Longitudinal studies

Household panel studies

following households over time and asking questions on a broad range of topics such as household composition, employment, earnings, health, social and political participation and life-satisfaction

- German Socio-Economic Panel (SOEP)
- Understanding society (and the British Household Panel Study)
- Swiss Household Panel

Five key data providing organisations

-
- 1 Eurostat – Statistics office of European Union
 - 2 LIS - harmonised socio-economic micro datasets
 - 3 OECD – key source of comparable statistical, economic and social data
 - 4 World Bank - Free and open access to global development data
 - 5 IMF - time series data on economic and financial indicators

Example data provider

Eurostat

Statistical office of the European Union

Provides national and sub-national data

- economy and finance, population and social conditions, industry, trade, agriculture and fisheries, transport, environment and energy and science, technology and innovation

Microdata.

- e.g European Community Household Panel, European Union Labour Force Survey, European Union Statistics on Income and Living Conditions

Metadata for Official Statistics

MISSY (**Microdata Information System**) is an online service platform that provides structured metadata for official statistics. MISSY includes metadata at the study and variable level as well as reports and tools for data handling and analysis. All documentation in MISSY refers to microdata available for scientific purposes. MISSY currently documents the following official statistics microdata:

EU-Data

- [AES](#) (Adult Education Survey)
- [CIS](#) (Community Innovation Survey)
- [EU-LFS](#) (European Union Labour Force Survey)
- [EU-SILC](#) (European Union Statistics on Income and Living Conditions)
- [SES](#) (Structure of Earnings Survey)

National Data

- [MZ](#) (German microcensus)

Microcensus (DE)

EU-Data

AES

CIS

EU-LFS

EU-SILC

Browse ▲

2016 2015 2014 2013

2012 2011 2010 2009

2008 2007 2006 2005

Cross-sectional

Select Variable List

Original Order	Thematic Order
Matrix ▼	
Setups	
Materials ▼	
Tools ▼	

Study: EU-SILC 2016

- Titles ▼
- Abstract ▼
- Coverage ▼
- Notes ▼
- References ▼

Country Specific Information: EU-SILC 2016

AT	BE	BG	CY	CZ	DE	DK	EE	EL/GR	ES	FI	FR	HR
HU	LT	LV	NL	NO	PL	PT	RO	RS	SE	SI	SK	UK

SI - Slovenia

- National Reference ▼
- Target Sample Size ▼
- Available Data ▼
- Sampling Procedure ▼
- Panel Design ▼
- Data Collection ▼

Source: [MISSY](#)

Series and studies for SLOVENIA	
	Census
	Central Population Register (CPR)
	Community Innovation Survey (CIS)
	European Union Statistics on Income and Living Conditions (EU-SILC)
	External Trade
	Final accounts
	Graduates in tertiary education
	Gross Fixed Capital Formation
	Household Budget Survey (HBS)
	Industrial production
	Labour Force Survey (LFS)
	Personal Income Tax
	Slovenian Business Register
	Statistical Register of Employment
	Student enrolment in tertiary education
	Time Use Survey (TUS)
	Unemployed workers
	Usage of information-communication technologies in enterprises
	Victimisation Survey (VS)

Factsheet: Accreditation & Data Access Conditions for SLOVENIA

Contact

Name

Statistični urad Republike Slovenije (Statistical Office of the Republic of Slovenia, SORS)

Postal Address

Litostrojska cesta 54 SI-1000 Ljubljana (Slovenia)

Contact

info.stat@gov.si

Website

[\[click here\]](#)

CIMES

Centralising and Integrating Metadata from European Statistics

Conditions

General Conditions

Microdata can be provided for research purposes to registered research institutions and registered researchers in both academia and government offices. "Registered" researchers have a national identifier. As a general rule, users submit applications for access that are assessed by a Confidentiality committee (internal to SORS); the latter prepares recommendations for SORS's board of directors, which makes the final decision.

Conditions for Non-Resident Researchers

Same as national researchers (though requests from non-registered researchers should be evaluated by the internal Confidentiality committee).

Source: [CIMES](#)

CESSDA ERIC

	Series and studies for SLOVENIA	X
	Census	
	Central Population Register (CPR)	
	Community Innovation Survey (CIS)	
	European Union Statistics on Income and Living Conditions (EU-SILC)	
	External Trade	
	Final accounts	
	Graduates in tertiary education	
	Gross Fixed Capital Formation	
	Household Budget Survey (HBS)	
	Industrial production	
	Labour Force Survey (LFS)	
	Labour Force Survey - 1995	
	Labour Force Survey - 1996	
	Labour Force Survey - 1997	
	Labour Force Survey - 1998	
	Labour Force Survey - 1999	
	Labour Force Survey - 2000	
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	Labour Force Survey - 2004	
	Labour Force Survey - 2005	
	Labour Force Survey - 2006	
	Labour Force Survey - 2007	
	Labour Force Survey - 2008	
	Labour Force Survey - 2009	

Study

Labour Force Survey - 2011

Original Title :

Anketa o delovni sili - 2011

Original Alternative Title :

ADS - 2011

English Alternative Title:

LFS - 2011

Producer : SORS.

Abstract :

Slovenian Labour Force Survey 2011 is a Slovenian research with a tradition. The LFS measures the labour status and other characteristics of the population in a certain week of each quarter, by spreading the sample uniformly over all the weeks of the quarter. The survey provides data on size, structure and characteristics of active and inactive population. Data on personal income are added to the dataset (DURS register) – an average monthly income in either the whole year or a shorter period of time, if a person had worked for less than a year. Approximately 19.750 individuals are selected to the sample in each quarter. Non-anonymised version of LFS microdata is available to researchers, onsite or by remote access. The survey was conducted as one of the surveys of the Eurostat Labour Force Survey which includes data from 27 Member States of the European Union, four Candidate Countries and two EFTA countries (Norway and Switzerland). Comparability through time and space is possible as Eurostat distributes Labour Force Survey data of other participating countries.

Keywords :

LABOUR AND EMPLOYMENT, SOCIAL STRATIFICATION AND GROUPINGS

Geographic coverage : Slovenia.

Universe :

The target population is the jure population, which includes persons that are mainly living in the territory of Republic of Slovenia, regardless of their nationality. Only the population, is living in individual households, is covered by the survey. Institutionalized people are not considered as a part of the jure population. Those who live in institutions (soldiers, hospitalized, imprisoned etc.) for more than 12 months, including students who don't live at home and Slovenian citizens who live abroad permanently or temporarily, are not covered by the survey.

Sampling Procedure :

The Labour Force Survey is based on the sample taken from the Central Population Register. It is a rotating panel carried out continuously throughout the whole year. The sampling method is stratified systematic random sampling of addresses. All members of the household at the selected address are included in the sample. That means that there are approximately 16 150 individuals included in each

CIMES

Centralising and Integrating Metadata from European Statistics

Source: [CIMES](#)

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Direct from project websites

Some research projects share research data through project websites

<http://cwed2.org/>

The screenshot shows the homepage of the Comparative Welfare Entitlements Dataset (CWED). The header features the CWED logo (three circles and the text 'CWED Comparative Welfare Entitlements Dataset') and three institutional logos: the University of Cambridge, the University of Oxford, and a blue circular logo. A red navigation bar contains the following links: Home, About, Data, People, Publications, Working Paper Series, FAQs, and Links. The main content area includes a 'WELCOME' section with a paragraph about the dataset's scope and an updated version. A box on the right lists the 'Principal Investigators' as Lyle Scruggs, Kati Kuitto, and Detlef Jahn. Below this is a red button labeled 'Download CWED 2 data here'. A 'NEWS' section at the bottom contains two entries: one dated June 22, 2017, about updated scientific works, and another dated June 09, 2017, about forthcoming publications.

CWED
Comparative
Welfare
Entitlements
Dataset

UNIVERSITY OF CAMBRIDGE
UNIVERSITY OF OXFORD

Home About Data People Publications Working Paper Series FAQs Links

WELCOME

The Comparative Welfare Entitlements Dataset (CWED) contains information about the structure and generosity of social insurance benefits in 33 countries around the world. Since September 2017, an updated version of CWED 2 containing a total of **eight household types** is available. The data contained here are an updated and extended version of CWED 1, which has been available since 2004.

This web site allows you to download customized portions of the CWED 2 data, browse the Working Paper Series or access documentary material.

[Download CWED 2 data here](#)

Principal Investigators:
Lyle Scruggs
Kati Kuitto
Detlef Jahn

NEWS

June 22, 2017 **Updated list of scientific works and papers is available**
More than 200 peer-reviewed scientific works are using CWED2 data. You can access an updated of all books, papers, and chapters in edited volumes using our dataset [here](#).

June 09, 2017 **Forthcoming publications from CWED members**

Data repositories

Digital archives collecting, preserving and displaying datasets, related documentation and metadata.

Types of repository

domain-specific trusted repositories (e.g. CESSDA archives) - focus on high-quality data with a potential for reuse

institutional research data repositories e.g. universities

general purpose repositories e.g. Zenodo, Figshare, Harvard Dataverse

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A registry of research data repositories.

Search

- ✓ by subject, content type and country
- ✓ for data archives with a certificate (a trusted repository), open access or for data sets that have a persistent identifier

2. Identify what you need

Four ways we can use archived data

New analysis: one or multiple data sources e.g. combine micro and macro, just secondary data or secondary data combined with primary data

Replication

Use of study design/methodology (e.g. data collection tools (interview schedules & survey questions) or sampling strategies)

Teaching : Subject-based or research methods,
Datasets made for training purposes – e.g. easySHARE

Identifying data needs

Research Question

- What is the ideal dataset for addressing this question?
(Compromises needed in reality)

Key concepts

How to operationalise?
(concepts can be complex and difficult to measure)

- Key features
- Multidimensional
- Groups of people
- Dependent/
independent variables

- What key features
- Multiple variables?
- Comparable/established measures (e.g. Schwarz Human Values)
- Standardised (e.g. ILO unemployment, ISCO, ESeC)

Identifying data needs

Activity 2

Identify data needs

Task: identify data needs - Evaluating data worksheet

3. Searching data archives

Three types of search

1. Search for data on a topic
2. Search for a specific dataset
3. Browse data collections by type or theme

Online catalogues – searching (browsing)

language

Search on site | På svenska

SND Swedish National Data Service

FIND AND ORDER DATA DATA MANAGEMENT DESCRIBE AND DEPOSIT DATA SND EVENTS ABOUT US

Order data SND Online Analysis Collections Data in Focus International data Questions & variables Accessibility levels

Home / Find and order data

Site map

Find and order data

Filter/sort

- Filter
- Kind of data
- Subject
- Principal
- Funding agency
- Availability status
- Series
- Geographic location

political attitudes **SEARCH** **i**

247 hits

Previous **1** 2 3 4 5 6 7 .. 24 25 Next

[Socio-political attitudes 1975](#) **Stockholm University**

The central aim of the study is looking at various aspects of political perception as a function of socio-political ideology. The politically perceived objects consists mainly of political parties, party-leaders and c...

- Bo Ekehammar, Stockholm University, Department of Psychology

Published: 1987 **1C**

[Socio-political attitudes 1979](#) **Stockholm University**

The aim of the study is basically the same as in Socio-Political Attitudes 1975. In the

ADP - SOCIAL SCIENCE DATA ARCHIVES

Analyze data! Deposit study! Promote science!

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Home | USE DATA | DEPOSIT STUDY | LEARN ABOUT | DISCOVER ADP | SEARCH

- List of studies by:
- Study ID
 - Series
 - Study topics
 - Depositors
 - Year of Production
 - Year of Publication
 - Author
 - International studies

Use data / ADP Catalogue

ADP CATALOGUE

Date of the last change of the catalog: 06.07.2018

List of studies by study's ID

Study ID	Study title, topic	Access
EUVET12	7 EU VET - Study on vocational education in seven european countries topic: EDUCATION, EDUCATION - vocational education, produced by: COI	nesstor
EWCS05	European Working Conditions Survey 2005 topic: LABOUR AND EMPLOYMENT, LABOUR AND EMPLOYMENT - employment, produced by: EUROFOUND	nesstor
EWCS01	Working Conditions in European Union Candidate Countries, 2001 topic: LABOUR AND EMPLOYMENT, LABOUR AND EMPLOYMENT - employment, produced by: EUROFOUND	nesstor
FEMAKT16	Intersectionality and Feminist Activism, 2016: Student Feminist Societies in the United Kingdom topic: SOCIAL STRATIFICATION AND GROUPINGS, SOCIAL STRATIFICATION AND GROUPINGS - gender and gender roles, produced by: None	nesstor

Study Topics

- DEMOGRAPHY, POPULATION, VITAL STATISTICS AND CENSUSES
- [ECONOMICS](#)
- EDUCATION
- HEALTH
- HOUSING AND LAND USE PLANNING
- INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION
- LABOUR AND EMPLOYMENT
- LAW, CRIME AND LEGAL SYSTEMS
- NATURAL ENVIRONMENT
- Not categorized
- OTHER
- POLITICS
- PSYCHOLOGY
- SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY
- SOCIAL STRATIFICATION AND GROUPINGS
- SOCIAL WELFARE POLICY AND SYSTEMS
- SOCIETY AND CULTURE
- TRADE, INDUSTRY AND MARKETS
- TRANSPORT, TRAVEL AND MOBILITY

Economic Morality (ESS2 2004)

Data/Variables - Round 2 (2004)

- ❶ Citizens should spend some free time helping others
- ❶ Society better off if everyone looked after themselves
- ❶ Citizens should not cheat on taxes
- ❶ Trust plumber/builder/mechanic/other repairer deal honestly with you
- ❶ Trust financial companies/bank/insurers deal honestly with you
- ❶ Trust public officials deal honestly with you
- ❶ Plumber/builder/mechanic/repairer overcharged you, how often last 5 years
- ❶ You were sold food packed to conceal worse bits, how often last 5 years
- ❶ Bank/insurance company failed to offer best deal, how often last 5 years
- ❶ You were sold things second-hand that proved faulty, how often last 5 years
- ❶ Public official asked favour/bribe for service, how often last 5 years
- ❶ How worried are you of being treated dishonestly
- ❶ Someone paying cash without receipt to avoid VAT or tax, how wrong

Source: [ESS](#)

Documentation often extensive

ESS Rounds

[ESS Round 8 \(2016\)](#)

[ESS Round 7 \(2014\)](#)

[ESS Round 6 \(2012\)](#)

[ESS Round 5 \(2010\)](#)

[ESS Round 4 \(2008\)](#)

[ESS Round 3 \(2006\)](#)

[ESS Round 2 \(2004\)](#)

[ESS Round 1 \(2002\)](#)

ESS8 - 2016 Data Download

The ESS8-2016 Edition 1.1 was released on 9th of April 2018. Please see [Version notes](#) for complete information.

Users are obliged to read the [ESS conditions of use](#). Please see [Deviations in data](#) for an overview of errors or deviations in different countries.

ESS8 - integrated file
Edition 1.1

Integrated files and documents

[ESS8 - integrated file, edition 1.1](#)

[ESS8 - data from Interviewer's questionnaire, edition 1.0](#)

[ESS8 - test data \(MTMM\), edition 1.0](#)

[ESS8 - data from Contact forms, edition 2.0](#)

[ESS8 - data from Media claims, edition 1.0](#)

[Guide to weighting of ESS data](#)

[FAQ: Combining data files, Renaming variables, Other data formats.](#)

[Fieldwork Summary and Deviations](#)

Survey Documentation

[ESS8 Data Documentation Report ed. 1.0](#)

[ESS8 Appendix A1 Education ed. 1.0](#)

[ESS8 Appendix A2 Income ed. 1.0](#)

ESS Findings

Findings from the European Social Survey are available in a number of publications.

[>>](#)

ESS Data Alerts

[ESS8 Swedish data removed - 09/04/18](#)

[ESS7 Error in INWMME and INWYYE for Netherlands - 12/02/18](#)

[ESS8 Error in INWMMS and INWYYS for Netherlands - 24/01/18](#)

[ESS8 Second edition \(2.0\) of Contact form data - 15/12/17](#)

Questions?

Questions regarding data or documentation, please contact essdatasupport@nsd.no

Integrated File – Download

[Download ESS Round 8 \(2016\)](#)

NESSTAR for online browsing and analysis

The screenshot shows the ESS DATA website interface. At the top, there is a red header with the European Social Survey logo on the left, 'ESS DATA' in the center, and 'NORWEGIAN SOCIAL SCIENCE DATA SERVICES NSD' on the right. Below the header is a navigation bar with three tabs: 'DESCRIPTION', 'TABULATION', and 'ANALYSIS'. The 'DESCRIPTION' tab is active. The main content area displays the title 'European Social Survey (2017). ESS Round 8 (2016/2017) Technical Report. London: ESS ERIC'. Below the title is a section titled 'List of Keywords' with a bulleted list: Trust, politics, social values, social exclusion, discrimination, religion, national identity, climate change, energy, and welfare. Below the keywords is a section titled 'Topic Classification' with a bulleted list: Social trust, political interest and participation, socio-political orientations, social exclusion, national, ethnic and religious allegiances, climate change, energy security and energy preferences, welfare, human values, and demographics and socioeconomics. Below the topic classification is a section titled 'Country' with a list of countries: Austria, Belgium, Czech Republic, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Iceland, Ireland, Israel, Italy, Lithuania, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Russian Federation, Slovenia, and Sweden. On the left side of the interface, there is a sidebar with a tree view of the ESS data structure, including 'ESS', 'Metadata', 'Study Description', 'Variable Description', and 'Administrative variables'.

- online data browsing and analysis
- download tables, graphs, data files and study descriptions
- main catalogue or additional tool
- help pages [? at top]

essda eric

Let's start with a simple exercise comparing **life satisfaction measures** of two groups – the **unemployed people looking for work** versus **people in paid work**. Calculate the means for the two groups across Europe.

Variable mnactic: Main activity, last 7 days. All respondents. Post coded

LITERAL QUESTION

F17c2. POST CODE: I

Values	Categories	Code	Frequency	% of all	% of valid
	Main activity, last 7 days. All respondents. Post coded				
1	Paid work	1	25,760	47.1	47.6
2	Education	2	4,704	8.6	8.7
3	Unemployed, looking for job	3	2,978	5.4	5.5
4	Unemployed, not looking for job	4	1,155	2.1	2.1
5	Permanently sick or disabled	5	1,291	2.4	2.4
6	Retired	6	12,819	23.4	23.7
7	Community or military service	7	90	0.2	0.2
8	Housework, looking after children, others	8	4,796	8.8	8.9
9	Other	9	520	1.0	1.0
66	Not applicable				
77	Refusal	77	39	0.1	-
88	Don't know	88	105	0.2	-
99	No answer	99	416	0.8	-
	Total		54,673	100.0	100.0

SUMMARY STATISTICS

This variable is numerical

Socio-demographics

- Doing last 7 days: no answer
- Interviewer code, one/more than one doing last 7 days
- Main activity last 7 days
- Main activity, last 7 days. All respondents. Post code
- Interviewer code, respondent in p
- Control paid work last 7 days
- Ever had a paid job
- Year last in paid job
- Employment relation
- Number of employees respondent
- Employment contract unlimited or limited duration
- Establishment size

- Add to row
- Add to column
- Use as filter
- Add as measure

DESCRIPTION TABULATION ANALYSIS

Dataset: ESS6-2012, ed.2.1

Choose 'Add to column' to place the variable here.

To populate this table you need to select a variable from the browse list, click on it and then add it to row, column or layers, or use it as a measure variable.

Politics

- Placement on left right scale
- How satisfied with life as a whole
- How satisfied with present state
- How satisfied with the national g
- How satisfied with the way demo
- State of education in country now
- State of health services in countr
- Government should reduce differences in income levels
- Gays and lesbians free to live life as they wish

- Add to row
- Add to column
- Use as filter
- Add as measure

B20. All things considered, how satisfied are you with your life as a whole nowadays?

	Median	Average	Minimum	Maximum	Standard deviation	Sum	Count
Main activity, last 7 days. All respondents. Post coded							
Paid work	7.5	7.0	0.0	10.0	2.2	179,423.0	25,653
Education	8.0	7.7	0.0	10.0	1.9	35,885.0	4,676
Unemployed, looking for job	5.6	5.4	0.0	10.0	2.7	16,028.0	2,956
Unemployed, not looking for job	5.7	5.6	0.0				
Permanently sick or disabled	5.6	5.5	0.0				
Retired	7.0	6.5	0.0				
Community or military service	7.6	6.9	0.0				
Housework, looking after children, others	7.2	6.6	0.0				
Other	7.6	7.0	0.0				
Total	7.30	6.76	0.00				

Source: European Social Survey, 2014

Main activity, la...dents. Post coded	Median	Average
All	7.5	7.0
Categories	8.0	7.7
Change selection...	5.6	5.4
Move to column	5.7	5.6
Use as Filter	5.6	5.5
Remove from table	7.0	6.5
Insert calculation	7.6	6.9
Permanently sick or disabled		
Retired		
Community or military service		

Change selection

Search for categories

All

- Paid work
- Education
- Unemployed, looking for job
- Unemployed, not looking for job
- Permanently sick or disabled
- Retired
- Community or military service
- Housework, looking after children, others
- Other

OK

Source: European Social Survey, 2014

FINDING DATA

ADVANCED SEARCH

Advanced Search - Mozilla Firefox

zocat.gesis.org/webview/velocity?mode=searchview&searchtype=advanced&&

Advanced Search

Search criteria:

Variable contains health + -

Search for: datasets variables

SEARCH

Study Description

- EVS 2008: Belgium
- EVS 2008: Greece
- EVS 2008: Integrated Dataset
- EVS 2008: Estonia
- EVS 2008: Portugal
- EVS 2008: Lithuania
 - describe your state of health these days (Q4) [Open in context]
 - do you belong to: voluntary health organisations (Q5aN) [Open in context]
 - how much confidence in: health care system (Q63M) [Open in context]
 - do you work unpaid for: voluntary health organisations (Q5bN) [Open in context]
 - kind of job respondent - ISCO88 code (Q112) [Open in context]
 - kind of job spouse/partner - ISCO88 code (Q118) [Open in context]
 - kind of job father/mother - ISCO88 code (Q129a) [Open in context]
- EVS 2008: Turkey
- EVS 2008: Azerbaijan
- International Social Survey Programme: Social Inequality

Variable v9: describe your state of health these days (Q4)

LITERAL QUESTION

Q4
<SHOW CARD 4>
All in all, how would you describe your state of health these days? Would you say it is

- 5 other missing
- 4 question not asked
- 3 nap
- 2 na
- 1 dk
- 1 very good
- 2 good
- 3 fair
- 4 poor
- 5 very poor

CESSDA data catalogue

Coming
Summer 2018

Search data collection of
all CESSDA members

The screenshot shows a web browser window with the URL <https://datacatalogue-dev.cessda.eu>. The page header includes the CESSDA logo and the text "Find Social and Economic Research Data". Below the header, it indicates "7163 results found in 20ms". The search results are displayed in a list format. The first result is titled "National Opinion Polls National Political Surveys; 2-7 July 1974" by "NOP Market Research Limited". The abstract for this result reads: "Abstract copyright UK Data Service and data collection copyright owner. The NOP National Political Surveys are conducted by NOP on a regular basis. These surveys are designed principally to ascertain public opinion on political parties, leaders and government, and to record voting intention. Data of this nature are given for each survey. In addition, the majority of surveys present data of topical interest and of social importance. +Main Topics: Variables Topics covered in the past include: Vot...". The second result is titled "Disability Follow-Up to the 1996/97 Family Resources Survey" by the "Department of Social Security. Social Research Branch". Its abstract reads: "Abstract copyright UK Data Service and data collection copyright owner. The aim of the survey was to find out the size and characteristics of the disabled adult population of GB. The research is based on a follow-up survey of disabled respondents in Family Resources Survey, 1996-1997, held under SN 3957 - part of a continuous survey of household characteristics, incomes and resources. Respondents who matched any one of a series of sift criteria based on age, benefit receipt or reported health...". A search filter menu is open, showing options for "Relevance", "Title (ascending)", "Title (descending)", "Date of collection (ascending)", and "Date of collection (descending)".

Finding data in practice

Searching can be hard

- Too many results
- No results
- Results not relevant

Evaluate search terms

- How well do they relate to your data needs?
- Spelling/language
- “Exact terms”, Boolean Logic (AND OR) – check how search tool works

Sort, filter, advance search

ELSST

Multilingual thesaurus of social science concepts

Hierarchical and non-hierarchical relationships between concepts

Use to

- broaden or narrow a search
- find terms used to index data in other languages

In future, ELSST will be used more widely to index data & embedded within search tool

elsst.ukdataservice.ac.uk

cessda eric

Activity 3

Searching for data

Finding data sources to examine ideas about cultural backlash

Task A

Use ELSST to select search terms

- <https://elsst.ukdataservice.ac.uk/>
- Find related, broaden or narrow search terms
- Terms in other languages

Task B

Search for data using a data catalogue

- Any national data service
- See CESSDA for links:
www.cessda.eu/Consortium

4. Evaluating data: quality and usefulness

The longer process

Research design (data management plans)

Consider the previous processes to assess data quality and suitability

- What information was collected, from whom, when and where?
- What has been done to the resulting data?

Metadata and documentation

Metadata ("data about data")

- descriptors that facilitate cataloguing data and data discovery.

Documentation

- user guides, survey questionnaires, interview schedules and fieldwork notes

- Catalogue records (with links to documentation)
- Quality can vary
- Efforts to improve data documentation
- Check for helpdesks/training

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What to look for when assessing quality?

Can I establish

- Why the data was created
- What the dataset contains
- How data was collected
- Who collected the data and when
- How was the data processed
- Any manipulations done to the data
- What quality assurance procedures were used

CESSDA Training Working Group (2017)

But is it useful?

Ask how it compares to your ideal dataset

- key concepts
- population
- geographical area
- time period
- units of analysis
- study/sample design

Activity 4

Evaluating data chosen

Evaluate the usefulness of found data
See worksheet

5. Accessing data

*“Now finally, I’ve found some great data,
how to I get it”*

- Licenses
- Access process
- Getting started

Data access arrangements 1

Open data

any user, no registering
(acknowledge source)

Registration

- often with institutional user name and password
- may wait for user name or password
- register use of data

Terms and conditions

- not trying to identify individuals, households or organisations
- not distributing data to others
- "data is for non-commercial use only" or for "use in research or teaching" only.

Download

from catalogue (but sometimes complete a request form)

Data access arrangements 2

- ❑ Sometimes permission from the data owners required (= a additional stage)
- ❑ Sensitive or confidential data = more strict (and lengthy) process
- ❑ Some services operate a dedicated safe room or safe access service
- ❑ Access by users outside the country can be prohibited for confidential data
- ❑ Free (except for commercial use and supplementary services)

If you are unsure, ask the relevant data service for help.

Getting started: using project-level and data-level documentation

What you might need to know?

- Folder structures and file names
- Version
- Case summaries
- Variables lists
- Exact question wording
- Questionnaire routing
- Manipulations to data and coding
- Weights
- Missing data
- Contextual details

Where to look?

- In a data file (e.g. summary of interview details before transcript, variable and value labels)
- Data lists (e.g. case summaries, variables lists)
- A user guide
- Fieldwork notes
- Technical report
- Readme files/version notes

And finally...remember to cite data

Why?

- It gives credit the data creators
- It makes data easier to find

How?

- Give enough information to locate the exact version of the data
- Look for recommended citation
- Use persistent identifiers (Digital Object Identifier (DOI))

CESSDA Training Working Group (2017)

ELEMENTS OF DATA CITATION

- **Author:** Name(s) of each individual or organizational entity responsible for the creation of the dataset.
- **Date of Publication:** Year the dataset was published or disseminated.
- **Title:** Complete title of the dataset, including the edition or version number, if applicable.
- **Publisher and/or Distributor:** Organizational entity that makes the dataset available by archiving, producing, publishing, and/or distributing the dataset.

- **Electronic Location or Identifier:** Web address or unique, persistent, global identifier used to locate the dataset (such as a DOI). Append the date retrieved if the title and locator are not specific to the exact instance of the data you used.

These are the minimum elements required for dataset identification and retrieval. Fewer or additional elements may be requested by author guidelines or style manuals. Be sure to include as many elements as needed to precisely identify the dataset you have used.

Source: [IASSIST – Quick guide to Data Citation](#)

ISSP Research Group (2017): International Social Survey Programme: Work Orientations IV - ISSP 2015. GESIS Data Archive, Cologne. ZA6770 Data file Version 2.1.0, doi:10.4232/1.12848

Hafner-Fink, M. and Malešič, M. (2016). Slovenian Public Opinion 2015: Work Orientation (ISSP 2015), Role of Government (ISSP 2016), Mirror of public opinion and National Security Survey [Data file]. Ljubljana: University of Ljubljana, Social Science Data Archives. ADP – IDNO: SJM15. Accessible at: <https://www.adp.fdv.uni-lj.si/opisi/sjm15/>

English Longitudinal Study of Ageing: Waves 0-8, 1998-2017

[Documentation](#) | [Related Studies](#) | [Publications](#) | [Syntax](#)

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TITLE DETAILS

SN: 5050
Title: English Longitudinal Study of Ageing: Waves 0-8, 1998-2017
Alternative title: ELSA
Persistent identifier: [10.5255/UKDA-SN-5050-15](https://doi.org/10.5255/UKDA-SN-5050-15)

UK Data Service
Discover

CITATION

The citation for this study is:

Marmot, M., Oldfield, Z., Clemens, S., Blake, M., Phelps, A., Nazroo, J., Steptoe, A., Rogers, N., Banks, J., Oskala, A. (2018). *English Longitudinal Study of Ageing: Waves 0-8, 1998-2017*. [data collection]. 28th Edition. UK Data Service. SN: 5050, <http://doi.org/10.5255/UKDA-SN-5050-15>

Select the text above to add data citation in your outputs.

Select citation format:

APA

APA

DataCite

Dataverse

Harvard

Vancouver

XML citation formats: [CSL](#) [EndNote](#)

SUBJECT CATE

Elderly - Social stratification

Social indicators and quality of life

Harvard

Vancouver

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Questions

*Pictures from
CESSDA Training Working Group (2017). CESSDA Data Management Expert Guide. Bergen, Norway: CESSDA ERIC.*